

ENHANCED IOT DATA MANAGEMENT USING NODEMCU INTEGRATED WITH GOOGLE SPREADSHEETS

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Abstract :

This study suggests leveraging the open-source IoT platforms Blink and NodeMCU to create a comprehensive system for monitoring temperature and humidity. Real-time data gathering and display for environmental monitoring applications is the goal of the integration. Sensor data is acquired using NodeMCU, and data management and transfer are made easy with Blink IoT. Furthermore, data preservation is accomplished through Google Spreadsheet integration, which provides a scalable and easily accessible option for long-term data retention. Temperature and humidity data are collected by sensor modules that are interfaced with NodeMCU as part of the system design. Data is transmitted to the cloud via the middleware provided by the Blink IoT platform.

Data is kept safely and readily through connection with Google Spreadsheet, making it simple to retrieve and analyze. Tools for visualization are used to display the gathered data. The gathered data is presented in an approachable manner using visualization tools, which facilitates trend analysis and decision-making. The suggested system offers a flexible and affordable way to monitor temperature and humidity, making it appropriate for a range of uses in industrial operations, agricultural, and indoor climate control. Effective environmental monitoring and management is facilitated by the integration of NodeMCU, Blink IoT, and Google Spreadsheet, which improves data accessibility, scalability, and visualization capabilities.

Keywords: Blink IoT, NodeMCU, Temperature and humidity monitoring, Google Spreadsheet integration, Data visualization

1. Introduction

The capacity to monitor environmental parameters like temperature and humidity is becoming more and more crucial in today's technologically advanced world, affecting many different industries. The need for dependable and effective monitoring solutions is clear, whether it's for maintaining comfort levels indoors, guaranteeing ideal conditions in agricultural settings, or keeping an eye on storage conditions in warehouses. In this case, utilizing the capabilities of Internet of Things (IoT) gadgets like NodeMCU in conjunction with platforms like Blink IoT and Google Spreadsheet integration offers a flexible and affordable real-time monitoring and data visualization solution. Building IoT applications is made easier using NodeMCU, a well-liked open-source firmware and development kit based on the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module.

It is the perfect option for projects requiring remote monitoring and control because of its small size, low power consumption, and integrated Wi-Fi capabilities. We can obtain precise environmental data on a regular basis by connecting NodeMCU to sensors like DHT11 or DHT22 that can measure temperature and humidity.

On the other side, Blink IoT is a feature-rich IoT platform that makes administering IoT apps, gathering data, and connecting devices easier. Blink IoT's feature-rich interface makes it possible for developers to easily implement IoT solutions without requiring a lot of coding experience. We can safely transfer sensor data from NodeMCU to the cloud for additional processing and analysis by leveraging Blink IoT's cloud architecture. Data visualization and storage are essential elements of any Internet of Things application. Here, Google Spreadsheet provides a practical and user-friendly framework for gathering, arranging, and storing sensor data.

Multiple users may access and evaluate data in real-time with Google Spreadsheet's integration capabilities and collaborative features. We can automatically log sensor readings to a spreadsheet by combining NodeMCU with Google Spreadsheet utilizing APIs like Google Sheets API. This creates a centralized repository for historical data. Furthermore, Google Spreadsheet provides strong visualization features that let users make interactive graphs and charts using the data they've gathered. Stakeholders can discover patterns or anomalies and obtain important insights into environmental conditions by visualizing temperature and humidity trends over time. A facility's capacity to check humidity levels or adjust temperature in a greenhouse, for example, depends on its ability to display data in a way that makes sense and promotes proactive management.

With this project, we want to show how easily NodeMCU, Blink IoT, and Google Spreadsheet can be integrated to monitor temperature and humidity. We plan to create a working prototype system that consists of a NodeMCU coupled to humidity and temperature sensors. The system will regularly communicate data to the cloud platform of Blink IoT. The information will then be sent to a Google Spreadsheet for analysis and archiving. We will demonstrate how IoT technology can be used to create flexible and scalable monitoring solutions for a range of applications through this integrated approach.

2.Related Works:

[1] An IoT Implemented Dynamic Air Pollution Monitoring System Sneha Edupuganti*, Narasinga Sai Satwik Tenneti, M. Mohamed Iqbal and, Gnanajeyaraman Rajaram The mechanism was designed to measure various air quality parameters such as temperature, humidity, various gases, microbes, and light intensity in real time. The proposed system consists of sensor nodes, a gateway, WIFI module, an LCD display, and a cloud server. The sensor nodes were placed at different locations to measure air quality parameters, and the data were transmitted to the gateway via wireless communication. The gateway aggregates the data from the sensor nodes and sends them to the cloud server for further analysis and processing. The cloud server processes the data, and the system also includes a web interface that displays data on the pollution levels of the air in real time.

[2] Design and Implementation of a Low-Cost, Wireless Weather Monitoring System Based on Arduino and NodeMCU,*, A. M. Khan, M. H. Bhuiyan, M. R. Amin, S. A. Azad. In this work, they describe an Arduino and NodeMCU based low-cost weather monitoring system. The device uses humidity and temperature sensors to wirelessly gather environmental data. This system provides a scalable and affordable method for remote locations' real-time weather monitoring.

[3] Mohammed Rakib, Sanaulla Haq et.,al., “IoT Based Air Pollution Monitoring & Prediction System” Proceedings of IEEE 2022 International Conference on Innovations in Science, Engineering and Technology (ICISSET) Date Added to IEEE Xplore: 23 May 2022. The proposed solution consists of two parts: an IoT device with four sensors connected with a processing unit and a software model. The sensors can track the pollution around us by measuring Particulate Matter, Carbon monoxide, Ammonia, Temperature, and Humidity. A microcontroller processes the data from the properly calibrated sensors and sends them to Realtime cloud storage through a Wi-Fi module. A remote server then fetches and analyses the data. We then determine the prime pollutant from the data, which is Particulate Matter. The Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model is used to predict the pollution levels from harmful gases & the Air Quality Index (AQI) of the next day with high accuracy

3. Methodology

A. IOT based temperature and humidity monitoring

In order to facilitate effective data storage and display, this paper integrates Google Spreadsheet with the NodeMCU and Blink IoT platform to provide a comprehensive framework for temperature and humidity monitoring. The central piece of hardware for data collecting is NodeMCU, a potent open-source IoT platform built around the ESP8266 WiFi module. In order to facilitate smooth integration with NodeMCU for sensor data transmission, Blink IoT provides an intuitive interface for real-time monitoring and control of linked devices. Through the use of Google Spreadsheet, the gathered data is reliably and easily accessibly saved in a secure cloud environment. Furthermore, Google Spreadsheet's integrated visualization capabilities enable users to quickly evaluate and comprehend the gathered data for insights and decision-making. A reliable solution for temperature and humidity is offered by this integrated approach.

Figure 1:Block diagram

B. NodeMCU Configuration and Sensor Integration

Our temperature and humidity monitoring system is built around the NodeMCU microcontroller, which provides flexibility and connectivity for sensor integration.

Because the Arduino IDE is compatible with the ESP8266-based board, it was initially used to configure the NodeMCU. We updated the NodeMCU's firmware with a custom build using the Arduino IDE, which allowed it to interface with a variety of different platforms and sensors. We used the DHT11 and DHT22 temperature and humidity sensors—which are reasonably priced and dependable—for the sensing component. The GPIO pins of the NodeMCU were linked to these sensors, creating a direct interface for data collection. Using the analog and digital input/output capabilities of the NodeMCU, we made it possible to monitor environmental variables in real time. The NodeMCU functioned as the main hub for data transmission, processing, and collecting in this configuration, guaranteeing a smooth integration with our monitoring system."

Figure 2: The schematic circuit

C. Software Implementation, Data Storage, and Visualization

Using the Arduino IDE, we create firmware for the NodeMCU during the software implementation step, allowing it to read data from the DHT11 and DHT22 sensors that are connected. We program the NodeMCU to gather temperature and humidity values at predetermined intervals using Arduino libraries. Furthermore, we use the Blink IoT platform to enable remote management and monitoring of the NodeMCU, giving customers internet-based access to real-time sensor data from any place. Additionally, for smooth data storage, we integrate Google Sheets with the Blink IoT platform. Sensor data is automatically sent to a specified Google Sheets document by setting up webhooks in the Blink platform, guaranteeing effective and dependable data storage. We use the built-in charting tools in Google Sheets to visualize the gathered data and provide graphical representations of temperature and humidity trends over time. These visual aids assist users to make knowledgeable decisions about resource management and climate control by giving them insightful information about environmental conditions.

Figure 3: Mobile application displays real-time value.

4.Result and Discussions

The gathered information, which is saved in Google Sheets by means of the Blink IoT platform, offers insightful information about changes in humidity and temperature over time. Informed decision-making is made easier in a variety of applications, including industrial process monitoring, HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning), and agricultural. Data analysis exposes trends, patterns, and anomalies in environmental conditions. In addition, stakeholders may more easily interpret and comprehend data visualized in graphical representations, which improves situational awareness and makes it possible to take proactive measures in response to changing environmental conditions. Overall, our findings demonstrate how well our monitoring system works to provide real-time environmental data for a variety of applications. However, they also point out areas that require more development and optimization in order to make the system even better in the future.

Figure 4: Mobile application display the previous history.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Date	Time	Temperature	Humidity		
2	20/04/2024	20:48:23	40	52		
3	20/04/2024	20:48:29	38.9	52		
4	20/04/2024	20:48:34	38.8	54		
5	20/04/2024	20:48:40	38.8	56		
6	20/04/2024	20:48:45	38.6	56		
7	20/04/2024	20:48:54	38.6	56		
8	20/04/2024	20:48:58	38.7	57		
9	20/04/2024	20:59:05	39.5	55		
10	20/04/2024	20:59:11	39.5	55		
11	20/04/2024	20:59:18	39.7	54		
12						

Figure 5: Storing the data in google spreadsheet

5.Future Developments

Integration with Cloud Platforms:

Examining how to store and analyze data by integrating with cloud services like Amazon Web Services or Google Cloud Platform. This would facilitate integration with other IoT devices and services, scalability, and advanced analytics.

Machine Learning Integration:

Use machine learning algorithms to examine past data, forecast environmental patterns for the future, and identify abnormalities. This could provide automated decision-making depending on environmental conditions, energy optimization, and preventive maintenance.

Energy Efficiency Optimization:

Using power-saving measures to extend the battery life of Internet of Things devices, particularly in deployments that are remote or battery-operated. This could entail making the most of low-power communication protocols, sensor sleep modes, and data transmission interval optimization.

6.Conclusion

In conclusion, a strong and adaptable option for real-time data collecting and analysis is the combination of IoT, NodeMCU, and Google Sheets for temperature and humidity monitoring. The solution provides a smooth and effective means to monitor environmental conditions by combining the data storing and management operations of Google Sheets with the connectivity and sensor capabilities of NodeMCU.

With the help of this technology, users may remotely view and evaluate humidity and temperature data from any location with an internet connection, improving situational awareness and facilitating quick decision-making. This system offers flexibility, scalability, and ease of deployment for commercial, industrial, and residential applications. In addition, the cloud-based architecture of Google Sheets guarantees data confidentiality, accessibility, and dependability, while the low cost and energy-efficient design of NodeMCU makes it adaptable to a variety of deployment scenarios. Furthermore, the system's interface with Google Sheets makes it simple to visualize, analyze, and share data, giving users the ability to get insightful knowledge and streamline procedures.

7.References

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